

SOME COMMENTS ABOUT THE HISTORY OF THE NATIONAL THEATER NAMED AFTER MULLA TOYCHI TASHMUHAMMEDOV OF KASHKADARYA REGION

Abdullayeva Zulayho Aziz qizi

2nd year history student of
Karshi State University

ANNOTATION: This article describes the history of the musical drama theater named after Mulla Toychi Tashmuhammedov of Kashkadarya region and the changes that took place in the theater before independence.

KEY WORDS: Theater, Mulla Toychi Tashmuhamedov, play "Halima", Sabir Vahidov, "Farhad and Shirin", "Tahir and Zuhra", "Layli and Majnun", "Alpomish", "Nurkhan", "Gulsara", 25 of 1932 - August.

In the first days of independence, Uzbekistan implemented changes in all aspects of society. These developments are also visible in the development of art, especially theater. Since ancient times, the theater industry has been important in reflecting people's daily lifestyle, expression of emotional experiences, and giving people peace and tranquility.

In the history of our country, the art of national theater has undergone a unique development and a rich cultural heritage has been formed in the gradual development of human society over the centuries. Today, I consider it one of the important tasks of not only the representatives of this field, but also of us young historians, to preserve the existing heritage and pass it on to future generations by restoring the lost ones. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "The level of development of our people is first of all assessed according to our national culture. In this sense, culture is the image of our nation and society. As we are starting to create a new image of Uzbekistan, we should start with the development of our national culture[1]".

The development of theater art in our country is especially important in the cultural history of Turkestan in the 10th years of the 20th century with the formation

of the new Uzbek national theater. Interest in the issue of theater began in the 1910s. Theater is considered to be the main tool for influencing people's consciousness. During this period, many national theaters were established throughout the region. In this period, one of the theaters created in our country is the musical drama theater named after Mulla Toychi Tashmuhamedov, located in Kashkadarya region. The establishment of a theater in Karshi has a long history. Before the establishment of the theater, there were bakhshis, hafiz, dancers, people singing folk songs in the Kashkadarya oasis. 1928 Kadir Abdullayev (resistance) organized an art circle in the city. After this circle became known among the masses with its concert programs, they gradually began to organize a theater. Our theater was founded in this circle on August 25, 1932 y.

At first, local artists' works were staged in the theater. According to the memories of the master artists, the play "Halima" was first staged in the theater. Later, the theater was used to promote Soviet culture and ideology. In 1936, this club was named the state theater at the initiative of Soibzoda, the head of the district public education department. At first, the theater was directed by A. Kadyrov, originally from the resistance. This year, the theater will be transferred to the state budget. In 1937, Ermatov started working in the theater as an artistic director, Sabir Vahidov as a director-pedagogue.

In the years of the Second World War, the theater performed its activities for the front and for the purpose of raising the morale of those who served behind the front, gaining confidence in victory. During these years, the theater was active. The staging of such works as "Farhod and Shirin", "Tahir and Zuhra", "Layli and Majnun", "Alpomish", "Nurkhan", "Gulsara" showed the maturity of the theater. In 1943, the theater was named Mulla Toychi Toshmuhamedov[4].

In the second half of the 20th century, the theater matured and made a great contribution to raising the morale of the people in the years after the war. This aspect is visible in the history of theater in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century.

In conclusion, we can say that the State Musical Drama Theater named after Mulla Toychi Tashmuhammedov in Kashkadarya is the only theater that existed in our region in the 20th century and served our people effectively.

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